

CONSTRUCTION OF PERCEPTION TOWARDS FAMILY ENVIRONMENT SCALE

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Abstract

The term Family Environment refers to all the objects, forces and conditions in the family which influence the child physically, intellectually and emotionally. Family Environment is an external factor and parents- students relations is an internal factor. The parents should try to provide healthy environment in the family because children spend most of their time in family children take up the ideals and traditions of the social group in which they live. Hence a proper social environment that children express their interest likes and positive attitudes. A proper, rational, healthy, atmosphere, atmosphere in the family enables the child to develop rational habits and rational attitude towards society. There is an urgent need to make more research on impact of family environment on various aspects of education. So, it was decided to construct a family environment scale for high school students. The family environment scale was constructed and standardized to measure the family environment of high school students. The steps followed for its construction and standardization are (i) Planning, (ii) Preparation of preliminary version, (iii) Pre-tryout, (iv) Editing, (v) Pilot study (Try out), (vi) Item validity and (vii) Preparation of final version. The researcher developed the preliminary version of family environment scale (31 statements) with simple, clear and concise statements for better understanding both in Tamil and English version. The validity for each item was tested. The item validity was calculated by finding the correlation between the total score and item score. Thus the final family environment scale consists of 23 items. This questionnaire was aimed at uncovering the perception of high school students about the family environment. This tool will help to find out details about perception of family environment of high school students

Introduction

The term Family Environment refers to all the objects, forces and conditions in the family which influence the child physically, intellectually and emotionally. Family Environment is an external factor and parents-students relations is an internal factor. The parents should try to provide healthy environment in the family because children spend most of their time in family children take up the ideals and traditions of the social group in which they live. Hence a proper social environment that children express their interest likes and positive attitudes. A proper, rational, healthy, atmosphere, atmosphere in the family enables the child to develop rational habits and rational attitude towards society. A healthy family is well ventilated; free of pests toxics, and dangerous gases, dry, clean, comfortable and affordable. Good construction and maintenance practices can achieve these conditions, even in an older family.

Preparation of Perception towards Family Environment Scale

Collection of relevant data is one of the most important steps in any research especially in the field of education. For this, an appropriate instrument or tool is very

essential. In certain cases such as may not work suitable. In such case the investigator has to prepare suitable tool, which will work adequately with the subjects selected for this study.

Steps in survey research

In this study the investigator wants to compare the perception towards value perception and family environment of high school students through the survey method of research. For that, the perception towards family environment scale was prepared and validated by V. Shankaranarayanan (investigator) and Dr. N. Subramanian (guide) in 2016.

Perception towards family environment

Perception towards family environment scale was prepared and validated by V. Shankaranarayanan and Dr. N. Subramanian (2016). It was titled as “*Perception towards family environment Scale*”. It is meant for the high school students and important considerations and procedures followed in the construction of the tool.

There are some general principles and procedures which one has to follow while constructing a tool. The major steps followed in the construction of the tool, H.E.S are described under difference heads (Shankala, 2007).

- i. Planning of the test
- ii. Item writing
- iii. Pilot study
- iv. Validity
- v. Reliability
- vi. Framing of final draft

I. Planning of the Test

The perception towards family environment scale prepared by V. Shankaranarayanan and Dr. N. Subramanian aimed at measuring the perception towards family environment of high school students.

II. Item Writing

In the process of item writing, the important step is writing of suitable item. After a thorough and careful study of the some Educational Psychology books and books related to family environment. The investigator collected materials and prepared a number of various aspects of perception towards family environment of high school students.

Table 1: Sample Distribution for Pilot Study

Sl. No.	Name of the School	Name of the Sample
1.	Seeniammal High School, Chinthamani.	25
2.	Hindu Nadar High School, Kadayanallur	25
Total Number of High School Students		50

This scale covers the decision features of the needed data. This method used in item writing was the fixed response method and the respondent has to select one. The items were

referred to experts for modification. As per their suggestions, some items were deleted and some were modified. The edited items were put up in a random manner including number of items for “Perception towards family Environment Scale”.

III. Pilot Study

A preliminary try out was made to find out the weakness and workability of the items. The difficulties in responding the items and rough estimate of the time limit for responding the item were noted. This step helped the investigator to modify certain technical terms, which were vague and questionable. For this purpose, the scale was given to the experts in the field of education and psychology. The investigator decided to have the items which are simple and the statement in easy to understand for the high school students. The investigator framed the items on two point scale, namely yes and no. After careful tailoring, 31 items were retained. The high school students were instructed to select the best option against the statement by marking a (✓) in the relevant column. The preliminary draft consists of 31 items. All the 31 items in the family environment scale are positive in nature. For positive items, a maximum score of 1 was given for yes and 0 for no.

IV. Validity

Procedure of validating the items is an given below. The row and the column of the table was assigned for number or respondent 1-50 and items were numbered 1-52 in the preliminary draft perception towards family environment scale of each responded were recorded in item wise table. The sum of the scores obtained by the entire respondent was calculated individually. The co-efficient of correlation between each item by all the scores of 31 items each scores was calculated using the following pearson product moment formula. The validity for each item was tested. The item validity was calculated by finding the correlation between the total score and item score. The table value for 5% significance is 0.26. The calculated value of each item below 0.195 was discarded and the items having the value 0.26 and above were retained. Thus the final perception towards family environment scale consists of 23 items.

Table 2: Selected Items

Item No.	r-Values	Selected Items
1	-0.07746	
2	0.192238	
3	0.409112	✓
4	0.307488	✓
5	0.20427	
6	0.543134	✓
7	0.401044	✓
8	0.147024	
9	0.355198	✓
10	0.410605	✓
11	0.411626	✓
12	0.531388	✓
13	0.320808	✓

14	0.208541	
15	0.411439	✓
16	0.574666	✓
17	0.406931	✓
18	0.585406	✓
19	0.625356	✓
20	0.247533	
21	0.390436	✓
22	0.386772	✓
23	0.342339	✓
24	0.39252	✓
25	0.502113	✓
26	0.513212	✓
27	0.224637	
28	0.340782	✓
29	0.551591	✓
30	0.370103	✓
31	0.188035	

A maximum score of 1 was give to yes, 0 for no.

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - X)(y - Y)}{\sqrt{(\sum(x - X))^2 + (\sum(y - Y))^2}}$$

r = Co- efficient of correlation

X = Mean of raw score of high school students

x = Raw score of high school students response in each item

Y = Grand total of score by each item

y = Mean of grand total score by each item

V. Reliability:

The items in the tool were divided into two equivalent half such as odd and even items and the two set of scores were correlated. By this split-half correlation method was calculated. Then the reliability of the tool was estimated by the following Spearman Brown Prophecy formula,

$$r = \frac{2r}{1 + r}$$

r = Correlation co-efficient

r = Reliability co-efficient of the tool

Thus the correlation, co-efficient (r) and reliability co-efficient were found to be 0.4082 and 0.6222 respecting.

VI. Framing of final draft

The final draft had 23 items. The items were neatly printed and administered the target high school student's record their opinions.

Conclusion

This questionnaire was aimed at uncovering the knowledge and conceptions of high school students about their family environment. This tool will help to find out the family environment of high school students.

References

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